

Research Article**Interleukin-6 Levels in Patients of Angina Pectoris**

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ABSTRACT

Objective; To determine the frequency of raised Interleukin-6 level in patients presenting with angina pectoris.

Methodology; This was a cross sectional study, conducted at Services Hospital, Lahore during July to December 2017. The cases of both gender and age more than 30 years were included. Angina pectoris was described with central crushing chest pain lasting for less than half hour along with normal cardiac enzymes with or without ECG changes of ST segment depression or T wave inversion. The cases with electrolyte imbalance, raised cardiac enzymes and end stage renal or liver disease were excluded from the study. The value of IL-6 more than 5 ng/ml was considered as raised.

Results; There were 100 cases of angina pectoris in the present study with mean age of 54.11±9.23 years. The mean IL-6 level were 21.45±10.03. There were 63 (63%) males in this study. There were 48 cases of smoking, 36 cases of HTN, 26 cases of DM in this study. Raised IL-6 level were seen in 66 (66%) out of 100 cases. Raised IL-6 levels were observed in 27 (75%) cases with HTN with p= 0.02. Raised IL-6 was also significantly high in cases that had DM where it was seen in 19 (73.08%) and in smoker where it was observed in 36 (75%) of cases out of their respective groups with p values of 0.03 and 0.01 respectively.

Conclusion; Raised Interleukin-6 level common and seen in every 2/3rd of the cases in AP and these are significantly high in cases with DM, HTN and smokers.

Keywords; Angina Pectoris, IL-6 levels, HTN, DM

INTRODUCTION

Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is a spectrum of disease and is one of the deadliest causes of death among both the developing as well as developed countries. It largely cover the two major groups of myocardial infarction (MI) and angina pectoris (AP). Myocardial infarction is classically labelled according to ECG changes and raised cardiac enzyme alongwith particular chest pain which is a common feature of both these entities. While angina is labelled as chest pain lasting less than 30 minutes without any rise in cardiac enzymes.¹⁻³ The underlying pathophysiology of all the subtypes of ACS is the same. Atherosclerosis is considered as the major cause for it providing a rough surface for the platelet aggregation and clot

formation; which can not only itself narrow the coronary lumen, but can also be embolic and can affect the otherwise. This ongoing chronic inflammation in the coronary intima led to the concept that in cases of angina pectoris these markers should be high and should narrow down the differential diagnosis of chest pain particularly in cases where there is normal ECG to document as AP. Multiple factors have been studied in the past and the most widely studied of them included interleukin-6 (IL-6), Fibrinogen, FDPs, plasminogen activator inhibitor-1, factor VII, von Willebrand factor, factor VII, C-reactive protein, VCAM etc. These markers denote the

vulnerability or instability of the atherosclerotic plaque.^{4,5}

The risk factors of ACS were the same in angina pectoris as well like DM, HTN, dyslipidemia, family history, hyperuricemia, male gender etc.⁵⁻⁶

IL-6, an intercellular mediator, belongs to hematopoietin family of cytokines. It is produced by a variety of cells in the body including T and B-lymphocytes, monocytes/macrophages, fibroblasts, endothelial cells and adipose tissue. This study was planned to see its level in cases of chest pain as it should be high in cases with AP as compared to non specific chest pain and can be life savior to guide further goal oriented management.^{6,7}

Objectives: To determine the frequency of raised Interleukin-6 level in cases presenting with angina pectoris.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

Study design; Cross sectional study

Study Setting; Services Hospital, Lahore

Duration; July 2017 to December 2017

Sampling technique; Non probability consecutive sampling. The cases of both gender and age more than 30 years were included. Angina pectoris was described with central crushing chest pain lasting for less than half hour along with normal cardiac enzymes with or without ECG

Table 01. Variables in the study subjects

	Mean	Range
Age (years)	54.11±9.23	30-71
Duration of angina (mints)	18.34±7.29	10-25
IL-6 levels	21.45±10.03	1-41

Figure 01. Raised IL-6 level in the study subjects

changes of ST segment depression or T wave inversion. The cases with electrolyte imbalance, raised cardiac enzymes and end stage renal or liver disease were excluded from the study. The value of IL-6 more than 5 ng/ml was considered as raised.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS;

The data was entered and analyzed by SPSS version 22.0. Effect modifiers were controlled though stratification and the post stratification chi square test was used taking p value of <0.05 as significant.

RESULTS;

There were 100 cases of angina pectoris in the present study with mean age of 54.11±9.23 years. The mean IL-6 level were 21.45±10.03 (table 1). There were 63 (63%) males in this study. There were 48 cases of smoking, 36 cases of HTN, 26 cases of DM in this study. Raised IL-6 level were seen in 66 (66%) out of 100 cases as shown in figure 01. Raised IL-6 levels were observed in 27 (75%) cases with HTN with p= 0.02. Raised IL-6 was also significantly high in cases that had DM where it was seen in 19 (73.08%) and in smoker where it was observed in 36 (75%) of cases out of their respective groups with p values of 0.03 and 0.01 respectively as shown in table 2.

Table 02. Raised IL-6 levels in study subjects with respect to confounding variables

Confounding variables		Raised IL-6		
		Yes	No	
HTN	Yes	27 (75%)	9 (25%)	p= 0.02
	No	39 (60.94%)	25 (39.06%)	
DM	Yes	19 (73.08%)	07 (26.92%)	p= 0.03
	No	47 (63.51%)	27 (36.49%)	
Smoking	Yes	36 (75%)	12 (25%)	p= 0.01
	No	30 (57.69%)	22 (42.31%)	

DISCUSSION;

Chest pain covers a wide differential diagnosis and is amongst the most common causes to present to emergency departments and medical clinics. In cases of normal cardiac enzyme to decided between angina and muscular pain is a great task and the former can be life threatening. Hence; there was always a need for a test to select the persons who are high risk for underlying coronary artery disease and IL-6 is one of these inflammatory marker. Raised IL-6 level, in the present study were seen in 66 (66%) out of 100 cases presenting with chest pain. The findings of the present study was also similar to the studies done in the past where they compared the different entities of the acute coronary syndrome with controls and it was seen that the IL-6 levels were high in not only angina pectoris but also in STEMI and NSTEMI as compared to the placebos and this difference was statistically significant; although no such cut off values were used and they compared the mean IL-6 levels with p values of 0.001 in each group. Lee and Yamashita et al, also showed significant high IL-6 levels in all components of ACS as compared to controls with p values less than 0.05.⁸⁻⁹ Furthermore, they not only found the raised levels but it was also seen the higher the levels of IL-6, the higher degree of severity was seen on angiography of the coronary artereries.¹⁰

The association of raised IL-6 was significantly high with respect to all the confounding variable in the form of DM, HTM and smoking in the present study with p values of 0.03, 0.02 and 0.01 respectively.

These are well studied risk factor and in multiple studies, they have revealed positive correlation

with atherosclerotic changes which releases IL-6 as one of the inflammatory marker. Luc G et al not only revealed higher IL-6 levels in such c morbid conditions but also revealed that this is associated with higher degree of mortality as well.¹¹

Lai et al, found this significant higher number in cases of DM only with p=0.02.¹² Studies conducted at various centers by Orak et al and Mehemuti et al also illustrated significant association of ACS subtypes i.e. angina pectoris along with MI with IL-6 with p values of 0.001 and 0.001.¹³⁻¹⁴

CONCLUSION;

Raised Interleukin-6 level common and seen in every 2/3rd of the cases and these are significantly high in cases with DM, HTN and smokers.

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